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““EYEEEEEEHHHHHHH!” (INAYAH AND AYANA’S CRY)”
Short and Sweet Play (Musical)

Setting:

A quiet and peaceful life in the mountains with tall trees and colorful flowers. Smoke comes out from the roof of a small Bahay Kubo. Inayah uses her delicate hands to weave dried pandan leaves while seated on a wooden stool. The golden hues of the late afternoon sun fill the clear sky.

(Soft beatboxing begins. A guitar strums a hopeful, exciting tune.)

Narrator/ Singer: (Guitar and Beatbox)

*Umnah iye ye umnah iye
Umnah iye ye umnah iye
Umnah iye ye umnah
Umnah iye ye umnah iye (2x)*

Scene 1: The Call of Home

Inayah: *(smiling to herself)*

I smell the trees,
the fire crackling, and the cool wind dancing
I feel the earth beneath my feet.
The whisper of home in every beat.

Ayana: *(with eyes full of wonder)*

We're in our land, barefoot and free
The Earth is our sanctuary
Every stream and every stone- our beautiful home

Inayah and Ayana: *(harmonizing as mother and daughter)*

Our skin is the gift of the sun, which lights up our way
our tongue, gift of the wind

Taking our hearts, through the mountains and
Through the sea.

Narrator: Eyeeeeeehhhhhhh

Scene 2: The City's Song

Amahin: (*looking up, hands behind his back*)
The horns of the vehicles and the newspaper boy
The smell of bacon wakes me in the morning.
I see buildings in the city,
Humming with the steel and glass around.

Charlotte (*City Girl confident and happy*):
The city is me, fast and bright
I'm one with the trend and the race
I chase dreams in heels.
The pulse of traffic lights,
With glam and rhythm,
my world is moving!

Narrator: Eyeeeeeehhhhhhh

Scene 3: Ayana's Dilemma

Ayana: (*to herself, unsure*)
I'm happy here, but something inside me wonders
I am longing for the outside world
To see what's beyond the trees and hills.

Amahin: (*reaching his hands to Ayana*)
"Come, come to your father, my child.
See the world."
I'll take you to the place where you want to be
you'll see what else you can be
Let your eyes and heart grow wide.

Ayana: (*turns to Inayah*)
"I want to go... Inayan, can I go?"

Inayah: (*pauses, breathes deeply*)
"Why do you need to go to the city?
You belong here.
This is your home.
Here, your ancestors sing.

The city is just noise,
And I won't be there to protect you.

Charlotte: (*smirks while scrolling her phone*):

"Songs? The city doesn't sing."
It builds, it creates. It shouts!
Who wants to weave baskets?

Ayana:

"I long to be a teacher
and give back to our people."

Tribesman: "*Let her.*"

Inayah: "Then go, my dear."
But always remember your roots

Amahin: (*In a warm, firm tone*)

Anayan, the wind brings change.
But don't forget your song.

Inayah: (*Weaving, without looking up*)
What use is a song if no one hears it?
The city takes what it wants, leaves us with echoes.

Charlotte, City Girl:

"Oh, the drama. You call it noise;" I call it progress and prosperity!

Narrator: Eyeeeeeehhhhhhh

Scene 4: The City's Embrace

Ayana: (*in awe*)

Every day I dreamt of this-
the bright lights and the towering heights
The noise, the pavement
Everything I imagined!

Charlotte (City Girl): (*bumping into Ayana*)

Ouch! What the ..?
What are you wearing?
You don't belong here!

Charlotte (City Girl):

Do you want to stand out? Or fit in?
Trust your dearest pretty sister
Blend in, be seen, be someone.

Scene 5: The Struggle Within

Ayana: *(to Amahin)*

Amahin, I've been thinking
Everyone dresses differently.
And I can't help but feel like I'm missing out.

Amahin:

"You never have to change to be loved.
But I'll support you no matter what."

Ayana: "Thank you, Amahin."

(Scene shifts. Ayana is wearing her city/trendy clothes.)

Ayana: *(excited and twirling)*

Amahin! Do I look great?

Amahin: *(smiles)*

Beautiful!

Ayana: *(turns to Inayah)*

Inayah?

Narrator: Eyeeeeeehhhhhhh

Inayan:

"You're not wearing all of that to school
Please clean your face, and lose your hair
Let your curls show."

Amahin: *(gently)*

'There's nothing wrong with what she's wearing.
I think she looks beautiful and fitting!"
Tied up hair is naturally daring!
And with our daughters' pretty smile!

Inayah: Please wear something decent, like ours
And a bare face with your natural smile!

Amahin: In this city?
She'll be stared at!
Look at the people around you!
Now you see you're the only one wearing that.

Inayah: I think we should go and get you back.

Amahin: No way!

Inayah: I'm the one who's been with her before.
I know you just forced our daughter with all of this.

Amahin: No. But our daughter loved it.

Inayah: No. She's not loving it!

Amahin: Yes!

Inayah: No!

Amahin: She does!

Inayah: Go!

Amahin: No!

Ayana: STOP!

I know both of you just want the best for me
And you're right, my choices should reflect me,
I am me.

AYANA: *(to Inayah, tearfully)*
Inayah... I feel like I'm standing between two worlds.
If I choose one, I lose the other.

INAYAH *(gently taking her hand)*
Then don't choose. Carry both.
We are woven from many threads, my daughter.
You don't have to cut one to keep the other.

Narrator: Eyeeeeeehhhhhhh

Scene 6. Resolution & Unity

Charlotte (City Girl): *(reflecting, quieter)*
Maybe...
Maybe it's not all about what fits.
Maybe it's about what matters.

Inayah: *(smiling with tears)*
Clothes change. Cities change.
But our hearts... our values
They stay

Amahin: *(nodding and agreeing)*
Go far.
Fly high.
But always remember who you are!

Ayana: *(smiling, pulling her sleeve back)*
I am who I choose to be.
I always carry with me my roots.
And I am exactly where I wanted to be.

(She reveals her tribal bracelet, it is small but it is powerful.)

All Characters:

In our differences
We sometimes feel lost,
But with it we find one another.
It's what binds us.
It takes us back to our roots.

(The light softens into a warm golden hue. Inayah and Ayana walk side by side—every step blending their worlds.)